

Synthesis, Characterization and Evaluation of Photocatalytic behaviour of Neodymium Oxide Nanoparticles

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ABSTRACT

Water pollution due to industrial dyes is a serious threat to ecosystem and addressing this issue is a significant challenge. Pure Neodymium oxide nanoparticles were prepared through co-precipitation method and characterized using analytical techniques viz, XRD, FTIR, UV-Visible spectra, Raman spectra, FE-SEM, HR-TEM, EDX, XPS etc. to address environmental remission. XRD Data obtained confirms the presence of Nd₂O₃ nanoparticles , FTIR and Raman peaks corresponding to different bonds confirm the presence of Nd₂O₃ nanoparticles , FESEM and HRTEM images confirm the Platelet shape and size of the synthesized nanoparticles and XPS data also confirm the presence of Neodymium and Oxygen and also their oxidation states.

Neodymium oxide nano-particles when exposed to visible light undergoes excitation leading to the formation of electron-hole pairs which is responsible for the oxidation or reduction of Methyl Violet Dye leading to formation of less harmful products. Neodymium oxide nanoparticles showed good photocatalytic activity wherein it could degrade Methyl Violet Dye and hence could act as a sustainable and efficient approach for polluted water remediation.

1. Introduction

The main pollutants of surface water are dyes. Presently, Advanced oxidation processes have come into light as an alternative to treat organic pollutants[1]. All AOP's generally work by generation of hydroxyl radicals[2-6] . Another efficient process is the fenton oxidation process [7].One of the best methods used so far is Catalytic wet peroxide oxidation(CWPO) method[8-10].In the CWPO method clay play an important role as a catalyst[11].Clay maybe modified by

pillarization to enhance its performance[12].The efficiency of semi conductors can be improved by doping it with Lanthanide ions[13-18] or they may also be coupled with semiconductor techniques[19,20].

Methyl Violet dye is cationic dye, which has a wide range of applications in paints, textiles and inks [21]. Cotton, silk, paper etc are dyed using Methyl Violet dye [22]. It is the active component in Gram's biological stain for bacteria categorization [23].During the dyeing processes, there is always a portion of applied dyes which is washed out. The unfixed dyes are found to be in high concentrations which pollute the water bodies. Since it is poisonous, corrosive, reactive, basic and flammable, it must be processed before being reused or redirected into the waters. Nanoparticles show efficient degradation of methyl violet dye under sunlight irradiation.

In the present paper pure Nd₂O₃ NP's have been prepared by precipitation method and their photocatalytic degradation of Methyl Violet dye was investigated under visible light. To the best of our knowledge , no report on photodegradation of MV dye in presence of Nd₂O₃ NP's have been reported so far.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

The chemicals used were all analytical reagent grade or chemically pure grade. Neodymium nitrate hexahydrate Nd (NO₃)₃ 6H₂O and sodium carbonate were purchased from Alfa Aiser (99.9%), and deionized water was used to prepare solutions.

2.2. Physical measurements

The powder XRD measurements were made using Rigaku, japan (SmartLabSE) diffractometer with monochromatized Cu K-Alpha radiation [K-Alpha + 1.5406 Å]. IR spectrum was recorded with KBr pellet on a Shimadzu, IPPrestige -21 model spectrophotometer. The Diffused reflectance spectra (DRS) of sample was recorded with Shimadzu (UV- 3600) spectrophotometer. The morphology and microstructure of the sample was recorded at BITS-Goa campus (for HRTEM, *Talos F00S G2*, for FESEM *Quanta FEG 250*, for Raman spectra : *LabRam HR Horiba France* instruments were used respectively), The XPS of the sample was

recorded using Kratos/Shimadzu Amicus (model: ESCA 3400). The UV-Visible spectra of solutions are recorded on Shimadzu (UV- 2600), model: TCC – 240 A spectrophotometer.

Origin Software (2025) was used to analyze the spectral data.

2.3. Synthesis

In precipitation method, the precursor of metal salt is mixed with a suitable reagent under a controlled environment resulting in the formation of metal NP's. Neodymium nitrate hydrate was used as a precursor in this method to produce Nd₂O₃ NP's.

Sodium Carbonate solution (0.1M) was prepared by dissolving 5.3 g of Sodium carbonate in 500mL of deionised water and this solution acts as the precipitating agent. Furthermore, this precipitating agent solution was added to hydrated Neodymium nitrate solution (0.1M) with vigorous stirring. A violet coloured precipitate was obtained which was filtered using a suction pump. This precipitate was washed with deionised water and dried. This violet precipitate was then calcined at 500⁰C for around 2 hours leading to formation of greyish-violet Nd₂O₃ NP's.

2.4 Photocatalytic measurements

The photocatalytic efficiency of Nd₂O₃ NP's under study was determined by degradation of Methyl violet dye under visible light. The decolouration of dye was taken as a model reaction for evaluating the photocatalytic activity of the nanoparticle. In a typical experiment, 50 mg of newly prepared nano-catalyst was added to 50 ml of 5 ppm, 10 ppm, 15 ppm and 20 ppm of dye. Reaction mixture was taken in a reaction tube and exposed to visible light (Tungsten Lamp) and stirred continuously. Samples were collected from reacting mixture for every 20 minutes upto 2 hrs. Each sample was analyzed using UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

The efficiency (% of degradation) of the photocatalyst in the visible light was calculated using the formula

$$\% \text{ Degradation} = [C_0 - C] / C_0] \times 100 \quad \text{----1}$$

Where C₀ is the initial concentration of dye solution and C its concentration at different time intervals of irradiation of solution under visible light.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Material Characterization

Powder XRD analysis: The detailed analysis of XRD and the assignment of various peaks are given in table-1 for the synthesized Nd₂O₃ nanoparticles under study along with standard values taken from JCPDS files for comparison [24-28].

Table. 1. XRD patterns of pure Nd₂O₃ NPs along with standard JCPD file data

S. No	Nano particles	2 θ (degree) values obtained in present study	Standard values of 2 θ (From JCPDS card no. 074-2139)
1	Pure Nd-oxide (Nd ₂ O ₃)	26.47 ^o (100), 28.31 ^o (002), 31.11 ^o (011), 48.58 ^o (110), 51.53 ^o (103), 56.19 ^o (112), 58.29 ^o (201) and 77.62 ^o (121)	26.8 ^o (100), 29.7 ^o (002), 30.7 ^o (011), 47.4 ^o (110), 53.4 ^o (103), 56.2 ^o (112), 57.6 ^o (201), 77.7 ^o (121),

Fig.1 XRD patterns of pure Nd₂O₃ NPs calcinated at 500^oC

Fig 1 shows the XRD patterns of Nd₂O₃ nanoparticle calcinated at 500^oC synthesized by precipitation method. The XRD pattern shown in figure 1 is in good with standard JCPDS (card No. 074-2139) conforming hexagonal crystal structure. Further, no characteristic peaks of

impurities such as earth oxides or other metal oxides were observed in XRD pattern showing the single phase sample formation. The average crystallite sizes obtained from Debye-Scherrer equation is **32.87 nm**.

FTIR analysis. The FTIR spectra of pure Nd₂O₃ NPs is shown in fig.2, reveals the characteristic band [24-28] of Nd-O (stretching vibration) at 433.98 cm⁻¹ along with other bands at 856.39 (C-O-C **Sym. Stretching**), 1093.64 (C-O Stretching) and 1398.54 (C-O Stretching), which may correspond to carbonate ions(used as precipitating agent) left after calcination. Further no impurities peaks are obtained which confirms presence of pure Nd₂O₃ NP's.

Fig 2. FTIR spectra of pure Nd₂O₃ NPs calcinated at 500°C

Raman Spectra: The recorded Raman Spectra is shown in fig.3

Fig 3: Raman Spectra of pure Nd₂O₃ NPs calcinated at 500°C

Raman spectra in fig 3 shows the peaks at 118 cm^{-1} and 449 cm^{-1} are assigned to F_g mode and combination mode of $A_g + E_g$ of Nd_2O_3 NPs as suggested by Mohd Umar Khan [29].

FESEM and EDX analysis : The FESEM images are shown in figure 4.

In FESEM images (fig-4 a, b & c) the morphology of the synthesized Nd_2O_3 can be seen, it is observe that the Nd_2O_3 NP's are somewhat flat flake like structure. The EDX plot (fig.4 d) clearly shows the presence of Nd and O elements which is attributed to Nd_2O_3 NP's.

Fig 4: FESEM images of Nd_2O_3 a)1.0 million magnification b)1.5 million magnification c)2.0 million magnification and d) EDX plot of Nd_2O_3

HRTEM, SAED and elemental analysis: Figure 5 shows the HRTEM, SAED images of Nd_2O_3 NP's and also demonstrates the elemental mapping of Nd_2O_3 NP's.

SAED image (fig.5 c) shows the uniformly distributed discrete spots which corresponds to the single crystalline structure of Nd_2O_3 NP's which is further confirmed by HRTEM (fig.5 a & b) images wherein all the planes of the NP's are in a single direction. Elemental mapping image (fig.5 d) shows the presence of Nd and O and their distribution.

Fig 5 : a) b) HR-TEM images of Nd₂O₃ NP's c)SAED image of Nd₂O₃ d)elemental mapping of Nd₂O₃.

3.2 Photocatalytic Studies

The photocatalytic degradation of Methyl Violet (MV) in presence of Nd₂O₃ NPs is presented in fig.6. All parameters, namely irradiation time, light source, concentration of Nd₂O₃, pH of solution were identical for all reactions for each concentration of dye (viz., 5 ppm, 10 ppm, 15 ppm and 20 ppm).

Fig 6 : Degradation of various concentrations of MV dye in presence of Nd₂O₃ NP's

The degradation of dye was evaluated using Tungsten Lamp as the light source. Absorption spectra were measured at regular intervals of time using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer for all experiments. It is found, that the intensity of the absorption band decreased as the illumination time under visible light is increased. May be due to availability of less active sites on catalyst. The degrading efficiency of Nd₂O₃ for MV dye was calculated using the equation-1. The obtained values for each concentration of dye are tabulated in table-2.

Table.2. Percentage of degradation of MV in presence of Nd₂O₃ NPS

S.No	Concentration of MV dye (ppm)	% of degradation
1	5	67.42
2	10	43.65
3	15	30.66
4	20	21.28

Mechanism: Once a photocatalyst is irradiated with radiation having energy equal to or greater than its band gap energy then the electrons get excited from valence band (VB) to conduction band (CB) leaving behind holes in VB. The photo generated holes and electrons further undergo oxidation and reduction process with water and dissolved oxygen resulting in generation of hydroxyl radicals (OH[•]) and super oxide radicals(O₂^{•-}) which are degrades the organic dyes. Thus photogenerated electrons and holes play a pivotal role in degradation of organic dyes into simple and non-toxic byproducts. Crystalline defects are often attributed to large surface area of the catalyst which favors the electron-hole recombination consequently reducing the reaction rate [30,31]. Also, it is often observed that on increasing the calcination temperature there is an increase in the crystallinity of the catalyst which in turn increases the number of active sites on the catalyst surface consequently increasing the photocatalytic activity [32-35].

Conclusion

The preparation of Nd₂O₃ NP's via precipitation method was successful which was further verified by various characterization techniques like XRD, FTIR, Raman, FESEM, HRTEM etc. The average crystalline size of the synthesized NP's was found to 32.87nm with the help of XRD. The FTIR and Raman peaks obtained also confirm the presence of Nd and O bonds

suggesting the presence of Nd₂O₃ NP's . The morphology of the nanoparticles was studied via FESEM which suggests the flat shaped structure of nano particles. EDX studies proves the presence of Nd and O atoms . SAED analysis shows discrete spots arranged in a regular symmetric fashion which suggests the formation of Single Crystalline nature of Nd₂O₃ NP's which is further confirmed by HRTEM images which show regular pattern of the particles.

The photocatalytic performance of these NP's was evaluated by its ability to degrade Methyl violet dye in presence of visible light. Various concentrations of Methyl Violet dye was taken and were mixed with the prepared Nd₂O₃ NP's under visible light for 2 Hours and then it was tested under UV-Visible spectroscopy and it was found that there indeed a degradation of Methyl violet dye. Thus, we conclude by saying the Nd₂O₃ NP's is indeed a good Photocatalyst.

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